

Supplementary data - Adapted CSLR process shared with experts for evaluation.

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Figure 1 illustrates the CSLR process shared with the expert participants, the activities highlighted in light gray did not undergo an individualized evaluation in the evaluation questionnaire. They were only considered in the analysis of the process execution flow.

Figure 1: CSLR process shared with the experts for evaluation. Adapted from [1]

References

- [1] B. M. Napoleão, F. Petrillo, S. Hallé, M. Kalinowski, Towards continuous systematic literature review in software engineering, in: 2021 48th Euromicro Conference on Software Engineering and Advanced Applications (SEAA), 2022.